

Significance of colour on room character: Study on dominantly reddish and greenish colours in north- respectively south- facing rooms

Maud Hårleman †, Inga-Britt Werner †, Monica Billger *

†School of Architecture and Built Environment, Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden

+46-8-790 85 23, maud@arch.kth.se, +46-8-790 85 59, ingabritt@infra.kth.se

*School of Architecture, Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden

+46-31-772 23 83, mpb@chalmers.se

Research paper

Space and Environment

Abstract

In this article we treat a study concerning room character due to colour appearance and spatial evaluation in different compass orientations. Rooms of the same colour, but observed in light from different compass orientation will appear differently; their identity colours will differ. The question now is if these circumstances are confined to colour impression or if they also cause a different room character.

A study is made in Sweden in the Northern hemisphere in which two rooms, a north and a south-facing were used, Ninety subjects, evaluated and compared the experimental rooms, equal in all respects except quality of light in 118 empirical studies. The walls were coloured consecutively in six hues in two nuances; the inherent colours were six pinkish and five greenish, plus one yellowish and one bluish colour. Room character was described aided by semantic scales. Data were statistically processed using the SPSS ¹ statistical program to analyse connections between spatial evaluation, inherent colour and compass orientation. NCS colour vocabulary was used. Finally, verbal descriptions with own words were used as a supplementary method to unfold nuances in response.

The study show that differences in hue and nuance affect evaluation of room character. Subjects reacted distinctly different on pinkish and greenish rooms; they had separate colour connotations. Room compass orientation resulted in different evaluation through weakening or strengthening of associations linked to the colours by colour connotations.

Keywords: colour appearance; spatial evaluation; emotional response; colour connotations; room character; light quality; sunlight and skylight, inherent colour; SPSS.

¹ SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) is further presented in page 5-6.

1. Introduction

Identically coloured rooms in different compass orientation will not appear the same in the Nordic countries. In clear weather, the south-facing room is dominated by sunlight while the north-facing room is illuminated by skylight and reflected light. As sunlight and skylight differ in luminous intensity, light direction and spectral characteristics, result is a major difference in light quality. Consequently, colour appearance differs between rooms despite being painted in the same colour, with the same paint. From tradition light in these locations is denominated as *warm* respectively *cold light quality*. How does this affect evaluation of room and colour?

Investigations into the effect of daylight on colour and spatial evaluation have been lacking. In teaching colour design, it is important to consider emotional response to these situations and to map out impressions of colour appearance and colour design in different daylight qualities.

We present a study grasping connections between visual appearance and significance of light and colour on room character. Main question concerns experience of room characters due to compass direction. What happens when rooms of the same inherent colour gain different identity colour due to different compass orientations? Chiefly reddish and greenish colours have been used, together with one yellowish and one bluish reference. Focus is on evaluation of space and room character. The questions are:

- 1 If and how do a room colouring affect evaluation of room character?
- 2 If and how do different daylight qualities affect room character?

The main aim has been to investigate the connection between verbal expression and emotional impression of room colours due to different light quality. Secondary aim has been to supply and test two new meaning variables; *embracing* and *elevating*. We named the study the ‘Red-green study’, yet the reddish colours are referred to in terms of ‘pinkish’, since reddish colours in the nuances used are generally called pink.

2. Background

2.1 Different approaches to colour

Osgood et al. (1957) introduced a psychometric technique with semantic differentials used with the factor analysis. In this technique, subjects mark a representative value for evaluation with the help of variables or *items* on a graded scale. The problem was to find appropriate items for the study at hand. They found that items could be grouped into *factors* and showed that three mutually independent factors represented the basis of most descriptive words; these were *value*, *activity* and *potency*. Research concerning subject's emotional reactions on colour, *colour emotion*, has a long history, in special among psychologists. Most studies on colour emotion have been made for single-colours or two-colour combinations (Wright and Rainwater 1962, Hogg 1969, Kobayashi 1981, Sivik 1969, Sivik and Taft 1992).

Küller (1972) developed a method for measuring and describing evaluation of built environment, the SMB- method. He found 8 factors; *affection*, *complexity*, *enclosedness*, *potency*, *pleasantness*, *unity*, *social status*, and *originality*. Küller himself particularly pointed out affection, complexity and enclosedness as important contribution to research on spatial evaluation. Hogg et al. (1979) worked with simulated interiors and found five factors for colour in spatial models: *dynamism*, *spatial quality*, *emotional tone*, *complexity* and *evaluation*. Over the years, the factors concerning colour emotion, have been looked at by many researchers (Kunishima, and Yanase, 1985, Küller 1986, 1991, Mikellides 1989, Sato, 2000, Oberasher and Gallmetzer 2003, Ou et al 2003 A, Ou et al. 2003 B). It was concluded that items classified under different factors in different areas of research, for example isolated colours, colour combinations, colour in spatial models and colour on exteriors. However, concerning interior spaces, the *value factor* and a factor for *activity* and *potency* were still consistently featured in most collations of factors encountered.

2.2 Connection between items and factors

Many studies dealt with colour and *temperature*. Using colour samples (Hogg 1969, Sivik 1969) it was found that the subject's reaction on colour is rooted in an experience of warm and cold colours. Warmest are red, (red, orange and yellow) and coldest are blue and green, (blue and blue-green). In full- scale experiments (Hogg et al 1979, Küller 1986, 1991, Mikellides 1989) it

was found that colours do not cause an experience of a physical temperature, but can instead cause a cognitive experience with associations of warmth and coldness.

Küller (1986) searched for, but found no simple connection between the *pleasantness* factor concerning hue and nuance. Greater differences were found between nuances within each hue than between different hues. Thus there was not a straight connection between nuance and pleasantness, and individuals evaluated the pleasantness factor with great differences. It was found that light and whitish spaces contribute to a sense of openness, and influence the size and form of the object. They also found that red colours had a more activating effect on subjects.

2.3 Real rooms with complex interactions

Billger (1999, 2004) has treated colour in real rooms with the complex interactions of form, light and colour. Her interest has been in colour appearance, colour change and colour description using complete rooms and artificial light. Billger emphasised the direct attention and conscious reflection of observers when in rooms. Billger found it valuable to use subject's verbal descriptions on colour appearance.

Hårleman accomplished two full-scale studies on colour appearance in natural daylight. Both studies concerned north and south-orientated rooms, and involve yellowish and bluish (2000, 2001 A, 2001 B) colours and reddish and greenish (2004) colours in two nuances. Stahre et al (2004) compared two studies on associations and emotional response on colours; Hårleman's (2004) room study and a study using colour patches (Sato 2000). It showed that the colour patches had to be much more colourful to give comparable associations.

2.4 Terminology

We have used the NCS system and adopt its terminology (Hård and Sivik 1981): *Colour* is thus defined as: colour percept, colour observation, colour perception; that which people see as colour and make it possible to make out objects and fields on the basis of colour differences. *Colour hues* in the NCS system are defined according to their relation to the four elementary colours: red, blue, green, yellow. Hue relation is shown through position in the colour circle. The colour triangle shows colour *nuance*, described as parts of blackness, whiteness and *chromaticness*.

Chromatic-ness is the sum of a colour's chromatic qualities. *Elementary attributes* are termed whiteness, blackness, yellowness, redness, blueness and greenness. Orange has thus *two chromatic elementary attributes*: yellow and red.

The term *inherent colour* is used to denote that colour which an object would have if observed under standardized observation conditions applicable when an NCS colour sample colour corresponds with its notation. An inherent colour can be determined operationally through comparison with NCS colour samples placed directly against object surface. The term "*identity colour*" evolved by Billger, is a term which tallies with a holistic attitude and should thus be interpreted as: main impression of what is apprehended as a single-coloured surface in a room. The term *experience* is used as an everyday term for mental and emotional excitation. Such experience can consist of feelings or emotional states, which arise in experiment room. These experiences or emotional states may consist of memories, associations and metaphors. *Room character* here functions as an overriding term for evaluation of a room with light, colour, space, surfaces and other architectonic elements. Finally, *colour connotation* as Sivik and Taft (1992) defined it: words having meaning not primarily related to colour. I use colour connotations for the idea or meaning suggested by or associated with a colour, a room colour or a colour word.

3. Empirical study

3.1 Experimental set- up

90 observers carried out 118 studies. Observers were architects and interior designers, plus students reading these subjects. Each observer made two complete studies, one in each room. Two similar full-scale rooms were set up in a construction cabin positioned facing north – south, measuring 4.2 m x 2.9 m each. Both rooms had similar short-end windows with white-painted frames and inner reveals. The inner surface of the walls consisted of plywood roller-painted with a new inherent colour for each test sequence. Floors were covered with beige-speckled lino, and ceilings consisted of white-painted roof boarding.

Figure 1 Experimental rooms

Two similar full-scale rooms were set up in a cabin positioned facing north – south.

The colours chosen were three pinkish and three greenish hues in two nuances commonly used in architecture- and interior colour designs. They were chosen to have perceptual equal distance.

The nuances were whitish 1010 and more chromatic 1030. The hues were yellowish pink (Y80R), pink (R), bluish pink (R20B), bluish green (B70G), green (G) and yellowish green (G20Y). Due to unsuitable weather conditions for a lengthier period, the pale yellowish green colour (1010-G20Y) was omitted.

One yellowish and one bluish inherent colour that were used in a previous study (Hårleman 2000, 2001 A, 2001 B) were included. These colours, reddish yellow (1030-Y20R) and reddish blue (1030-R80B), showed interesting patterns of hue shift, and could serve as reference points between the studies.

Figure 2a Selected colours.

2b Nuance NCS 1010 and 1030.

Three hues in two nuances, in total six pinkish and five greenish colours.

3.2 Empirical methods and procedure

Room and colour were observed and evaluated with qualitative methods, such as *semantic scales* and *verbal description*. The *semantic scales* were graded from zero to six, with six being the maximum, covering a value from 'not at all' to a value 'to a high degree'. That is a type called *Likert - scales* and not semantic differentials in the sense that they covered a scale from one position to its opposite. Observers noted their experience with a value for each *item* and 16 different items were used. Established items for spatial experience were selected and grouped under four *factors: temperature, spatial quality, dynamism* and *emotional factor*. Two new variables for experience were added to the already established; *embracing* and *elevating*, associated to the emotional factor.

A parallel method for *verbal description* was developed to catch the initial experience of room and colour. Observers were encouraged to note down own thoughts and descriptive words. The given tasks were twofold, (1) *Describe your impression of the wall colour* and, (2) *Describe your impression of the room character*. The room description (2) was preferable and the wall colour description (1) was used as a complement. The observers were instructed verbally to take their time for the process of experience and association. It was important that first impressions should

not be by-passed and that evaluations and experience of the room were allowed to develop. Just as eyes must adapt to a light situation, so must experience as a whole have time to adapt in a certain spatial situation.

The walls in two full-scale rooms were painted in the same inherent colour. Observation was thus confined to one room at a time. Instructions were provided for working process and *questionnaire*. The observers stayed in each room without any interruption, in order to adapt to prevailing light and experiment situation. In the initial phase the method for verbal description was performed. Following the more relaxed introduction, concentrated attention was required.

3.3 Methods of analysis

The full data material is made up of studies in two compass orientations, and with six colour hues in two nuances. Data were processed statistically using the SPSS statistical program.

A. Factor analyse.

To reduce data, factor analysis was applied on the whole data set, data from all inherent colours. This method generated new variables for further analyses.

B. T-tests.

T-tests were used to analyze differences in evaluation between rooms in different colours and locations.

C. Two-way analysis of variance.

To test the effect on evaluation by colour and location respectively an analysis of variance was carried out.

D. Verbal descriptions.

Verbal descriptions from the studies were made use of. These descriptions were divided into three, one for each of the compass directions north and south respectively, and one group for expressions in common for the two.

4. Study results

4.1 New variables for room character

The factor analysis was carried out for all observations, through all hues and nuances, using the Principal Components extraction method. To accentuate differences in factor loadings a Varimax Rotation was applied and five new components with Eigenvalues > 1 , were constructed. The first three explained in all 54,6 % of the total variance, together with the remaining two they explained 67,7% of the total variance. The percentage under the name of the component shows the amount of variance explained by the component respectively.

Following the factor analysis, four new variables were constructed to reduce data. The values of these four new variables were calculated as the mean of the included items (Kline 1995). Items with negative factor loadings were not included in the calculation. Working as mirror images of their opposites they would have confounded the values of factor variables by levelling out the calculated mean values.

Elevating	Harsh	Embracing	Peaceful
Elevating	Hard	Embracing	Tranquil
Merry	Cold	Small	Pleasant
Vivid	Formal	Dry	
Sunny	Dry		
Pleasant			
Warm			

Table A New variables for room character

4.2 Impact caused by colour or location

T-tests were employed to test for the impact of hue and location on spatial experience. They showed that there were some significant differences in the perception of the rooms. When using the whole data set there was an indication, but not statistically significant, that the location facing north was less related to an elevating character. When the data set was grouped into sub-

samples of colour in two nuances, this difference was significant for the group consisting of yellowish pinks and bluish greens.

Pink rooms were evaluated as less 'Harsh' and more 'Embracing' than were green rooms. The 'Embracing' character includes a stitch of a cramped condition and this was more explicit in both pink and yellowish pink rooms than in green and bluish green rooms. Also the pink rooms were perceived as more distinct than the green ones. Comparison between the sub-group yellowish pink and bluish pink did not show any significant difference.

4.3 Close-up on effects due to hue and orientation

A two-way analysis of variance was used to explain the effects from colour in relation to the effects of location, and effects of mutual interaction. The studied variables were the same as in the t-tests; 'Elevating, Harsh, Embracing, Peaceful' and 'Distinct.' The analysis showed an explicit effect by differences in colour. Regarding pink and green hues, the main part of the variance explained stemmed from different hue. It means that difference between room evaluations is bigger between red and green colour than between different locations. Generally, the nuance 1030, did affect both positive and negative emotional items more than the lighter 1010 nuances.

4.4 Colour connotations in verbal description

The observers used a variety of expressions to describe room character and differences between them. Most obvious was that greenish and pinkish rooms evoked different colour connotations. Pinkish rooms caused associations of human skin, facial colour, strong emotional expressions such as affection and defiance, and other mental characteristics while greenish rooms caused associations of nature and pause. Greenish rooms represented an opposite idea – nature pictures an otherness that could be either pure nature or artificial. Within these fields of associations observers had all sorts of different perspectives.

Some observers described the pinkish rooms as warm, gentle and stimulating but others experienced those rooms as pushy, demanding and glaring. Some experienced them as childish, young, fresh and funny while yet others described them as un-fresh, tasteless, vulgar and slovenly. While pinkish rooms produced images of skin, associations treated whether it was *dressed* or *naked*, whether it represented small *children* or *adults*, and whether it was *sweet* or *trying*, *innocent* or *sinful*.

Greenish colour connotation was of a completely different kind. Greenish rooms evoked connotations of *nature*, and *relaxation*. These rooms projected a shadow, an image of a landscape, or an unrestricted space. These in turn caused associations of pause; a retreat or shelter; elements like water and wind and objects and rooms like a pool or a bathroom. Greenish rooms also caused associations on *health*. Many observers described them as *clean* and *pure* and the double perspectives treated whether the room was unattached or influenced by artificiality as *living and plastic*². Frequent adjectives used in greenish rooms are *calm*; *peaceful*; *light hearted*; *confident*; *relieve*; *reduce*; *ease*; *soothe* and *tranquillity*.

4.5 Verbal description due to compass directions

As observers reacted to situations and different identity colours due to location, this showed as variations in character. Different physical qualities emphasised characters included in the colour connotation. In the strongly illuminated south-facing room, inherent colours with a yellowish content (G20Y, Y20R and Y80R), appear with surprisingly chromatic intense. Thus, connotations linked to these colours were experienced and expressed in stronger verbal nuances. Concerning the pinkish rooms with connotations to human skin and mental characteristics, differences in visual impact made observers experience variations in character as: sweet – foe, pure – sophisticated etc. Y20R and Y80R were considered as *soft* and *fluffy* in the south-facing room, and in north having less (or null) yellowish attribute, the room was considered as *more bare* and *empty*, more *hard* and *cold in comparison*. Elementary red (R) in the south-facing room appeared as yellowish pink and was portrayed as *childish*, *pure* and *innocent*. In the north-facing room, it was bluish pink and represented *impurity*, *sophistication* and even *adulterate*.

² In Swedish: levande och plastig.

As the greenish rooms evoked other associations, characters also varied. *Nature and quiescent, slow and tranquil* were common descriptions for both rooms, together with *clean and fresh*. Elementary green (G) in the north-oriented room, (BG identity colour) made observers describe the room experience as *uneasy to grasp, alive or plastic, disgusting or restful, pushy or relaxing*. The south-oriented room of the same colour, (G identity colour) caused associations as *warm, calm, soothing, embracing, still and gloomy*. In short these rooms may be recalled as *cool and neutral* respectively *warm and calm*.

	1030-Y80R	1030-R	1030-R20B
NORTH	Intense Darker Colder	Cold Alive Adult	Screaming Absurd Cheering
Both compass orientations	Snug, Secure Embracing	Soft Pushy	Nostalgic Strong
	Pushy Dominant	Importunate Trying	Independant Unfresh
SOUTH	Soft Fluffy Energetic, Alive	Warm Young Relaxing	Brave Cheerful, Funny Romantic

Figure 3 Differences in verbal descriptions between the rooms

Most frequently used verbal descriptions when evaluating pinkish rooms in the north- respectively south compass direction. The middle section shows descriptions in common for the two.

	1030-G20Y	1030-G	1030-B70G
NORTH	Dissociation Artificial	Alive versus plastic Disgusting versus restful	Dignified Restrained
Both compass orientations	Calm Unsophisticated Clumsy, Sad	Fresh Clean Tranquil Slow	Calm Cool Fresh Pure Intense
SOUTH	Warm	Warm Calm Embracing Soothing	Warm Empty

Figure 4 Differences in verbal descriptions

Most frequently used verbal descriptions when evaluating greenish rooms in the north- respectively south compass direction. The middle section shows descriptions in common for the two.

5. Discussion

5.1 Compiled analysis

Summing up, it can be stated that beside the overriding effect from difference in colour on room evaluation, also difference in location is statistically significant. It seems that colour connotations provide an instant starting point, or a field from where associations originated. The elementary qualities of pink and green aroused certain expectations of evaluation content: *perhaps the colour did not suit the experiment- room; it was feminine, private and childish*. Thereafter, the actual identity colour causes a calibration into a second impression: *the description of north-facing rooms as vivid was due to the intensely chromatic bluish pink identity colours*. In the act of recognizing, accepting and experiencing the room colour this colour connotation function as a basic idea with what the specific colour impression is compared. The general colour connotation seemed to be calibrated via associations from identity colour, as a confirmation or a denial of the given character and different perspectives on this: *negative reactions related to the same*

categories as the positive did: it could be too merry and vivid or not pleasant and embracing enough. This way, evaluation as a whole can be described through attaching descriptive words to a set context. It reflects cultural, traditional, sociological, or subjective meaning, a colour connotation express (indirectly) a certain condition.

5.2 New variables and items

The SPSS methods provided clear results though without the supplementary view in the verbal description, a compilation and understanding of the complex relations between location, hue, nuance and evaluation would not have been possible.

The original factors represented mutual exclusive categories: *temperature, emotional tone, spatial quality* and *dynamism*. None of these original factors remain and most of the items have changed places. The new variables represent four emotional variables with overlapping characters, and one separate variable concerning spatial quality. They are not comparable as they emerge from different ways to measure data; semantic differential scales versus semantic scales allowing a more differentiated and qualitative information. The ‘Elevating’ variable was essential in describing room character; warm colours and the more chromatic nuance increase *merry*, and *pleasing* emotional experiences. The ‘Distinct’ variable correlated well with the observation of warm colours as proceeding while the cold ones seem to be receding. As the cold bluish and greenish walls seemed to withdraw they consequently made an un-distinct impression.

5.3 Comparisons between studies

Pink aroused strongest emotional reactions, regarding both positive and negative character. The conclusion made by Hogg et al (1979) that the warmth factor more often expresses an emotional tone more than temperature is confirmed. Sivik (1970) has also pointed out that pink, and in particular bluish-pink, often is described in negative terms such as *ugly, disagreeable* and *unappetising*. We can see a clear relation between these negative evaluations from pink colour samples and room character.

The new variable ‘Embracing’, previously belonging to the emotional factor, was grouped together with *small* and *closed (not open)*. This tally well with Küller’s conclusion (1986) concerning the word-scales closed – airy and small – large, as being not fully correlated. Rooms

assessed as large could just as well be perceived as enclosed. Evidently 'Embracing' is not only a spatial scale for emotional tone but also for a cramped sense.

However, trying to find connections between items and factors can be hazardous. As often many items compose a factor, it is hard to find a perfect name including the true content. There is no standard procedure to help with the naming process and this makes it even more difficult to compare connections between colour emotion factors and colour attributes. A clearly positive evaluation in preference for warm colours did crystallise. This could be expected with subjects as a cross-section of the population but is an interesting result for architects and student architects. This unexpected tendency is worth making note of as several researchers (Hogg et al 1979, Janssens 1984) have presented evidence that preferences of architects often differ to those of non-architects, being considered to prefer stricter and cooler objects. This might indicate a wider application of the presented results.

6. Conclusion

- We propose three new variables concerning experience of room character.

The methods used helped to explore experience of room and colour in new sensible variables.

The new variables are 'Elevating, Harsh' and 'Embracing.'

- The study offers a new perspective for colour experience in rooms.

We were able to collect a great amount of evaluation values into a bigger pattern, thus easier to grasp connections between visual appearance and evaluation of colour.

- Hue and nuance clearly rendered a common experience in colour connotations.

Spatial evaluation was firmly bound to the identity colour. Pinkish and greenish colours caused almost opposing room characters. The difference between warm and cold colours was clearest.

- The compass directions resulted in different variance in room character.

As north and south-facing rooms of the same inherent colour gain different identity colours, rooms make different impact and observers react differently. The room compass orientation affected spatial character, by means of a strengthening or weakening of colour attribute. To some degree, the compass orientations had their own spatial character.

7. References

Billger, M. (2004) "The Experience of the Painted Room: The Significance of Light and Colour Combinations." In proceedings, *AIC 2004*, Porto Alegre, Brazil, 2-5 Nov

Billger, M. (1999) *Colour in Enclosed Space*. (Doctoral dissertation) Department of Building Design, Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden. ISBN 91-7197-820 8.

Hogg, J., Goodman, S., Porter, T., Mikkilides, B. and Preddy, D.E. (1979) "Dimensions and determinants of judgements of colour samples and a simulated interior space by architects and non- architects." *British Journal of Psychology*, 70, pp. 231-242.

Hogg, J. A. (1969) "A principal components analysis of semantic differential judgements of single colours and colour pairs." *Journal of General Psychology*. 80: 129-140.

Hård, A. and Sivik, L. (1981) "NCS – Natural Colour System: A Swedish Standard for Color Notation." *Color Research and Application*, Vol. 6, No.3

Hårleman, M (2004) "Colour emotion in full-scale rooms" In proceedings, *AIC 2004*, Porto Alegre, Brasil.

Hårleman, M. (2001a) "Colour Appearance in Different Compass Orientations." *Nordic Journal of Architectural Research*. No 2, 2001.

Hårleman, M (2001b) "Colour appearance of interior daylight: observations of hue shifts in different compass orientations." In proceedings, *AIC Color 2001*, Rochester, USA. Volume 4421, page 69-71. ISBN: 0-8194-4128-7.

Hårleman, M. (2000) *Färg i norr och södervettande rum. Kulörtonförskjutning genom varierande ljusförhållanden*, KTH, Stockholm. ISBN 91-7170-590-2.

Janssens, J. (1984) *Looking at buildings – individual variations in the perception of building exteriors*. School of Arch., Lund Institute of Technology, Lund, Sweden.

Kline, P. (1995) *The handbook of psychological testing*. London: Routledge

Kunishima, M. and Yanase, T. (1985) "Visual effects of wall colours in living rooms." *Ergonomics* vol. 28, No 6, pp. 869-882.

Küller, R. (1991) "Environment assessment from a neuropsychological perspective." In Gärling, T. and Evans, G. (Eds), *Environment, cognition and action*. Oxford University Press, Inc. New York. ISBN 0-19-506220-5

Küller, R. (1986) "Physiological and psychological effects of illumination and colour in the interior environment." *Journal of Light and the Visual Environment*, 10 (2), 33-37

Küller, R. (1972) *A semantic model for describing perceived environment*. (Doctoral dissertation), Document: 12. Stockholm: National Swedish Institute for Building Research.

Mikellides, B. (1989) *Emotional and behavioural reactions to colour in the build environment*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. Oxford: Oxford Polytechnic.

Oberasher, L. and Gallmetzer, M. (2003) *Colour and Emotion*. Psychology of Architecture and Design. Proceedings of *AIC 2003* Bangkok.

Ou, L.C. and Luo, M. R. and Woodcock, A. and Wright, A. (2003 a) "A Study of Colour Emotion and Colour Preference. Part I: Colour Emotions for Single Colours." *Color research and application*, Vol 29, Issue 3, Pages 232-240.

Ou, L.C. and Luo, M. R. and Woodcock, A. and Wright, A. (2003 b) "A Study of Colour Emotion and Colour Preference Part II: Colour Emotions for Two- Colour Combinations." *Color research and application*, Vol 29, Issue 4, Pages 292-298.

Osgood, C. E., Tannenbaum, P.H., Suci, G. J. (1957) *The Measurement of Meaning*. Urbana, University of Ill. Press.

Sato, T. Kajiwara, K. Hoshino, H. Nakamura, T. (2000) Quantitative evaluation and categorising of human emotion induced by colour. *Adv Colour Sci Technol* 2000;3:53–59.

Sivik, L. (1995), "Om färgers betydelse," in *Upplevelse av färg och färgsatt miljö*, Byggnadsforskningsrådet. ISBN 91-540-5696-9

Sivik, L. and Taft, C. (1992) *Colour combinations and associated meanings – semantic dimensions and colour chords*. University of Gothenburg. Gothenburg's Psychological Reports. Volume 1.

Sivik, L. and Taft, C. (1989) *Semantic Variables for Judging Color Combinations – An analysis of Semantic dimensions*. Göteborg Psychological Reports, 19, No 5.

Sivik, L. (1970) "Om färgers betydelser – perceptiva färgdimensioner relaterade till associativa betydelsevariabler." Skandinaviska Färginstitutet AB. Färgrapport F09, Stockholm, Sweden. (1969) (Colour connotations and perceptible variables.) In proceedings, *AIC Color 69*. Vol 1 & II, pp. 1064-1072. Stockholm.

Stahre, B. and Hårleman, M. and Billger, M. (2004) "Colour Emotions in Larger and Smaller Scale" In proceedings, *AIC 2004*, Porto Alegre, Brasil.

Wright and Rainwater, (1962) The meanings of color. *Journal of general psychology* 67, pages 89-99.